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COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE EFFICIENCY OF LIVER RADIAL DIAGNOSIS IN HEPATITIS

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Annotation: Based on the data presented in the Internet sources, an analysis of the effectiveness of the use of methods of radiation diagnosis of the liver in hepatitis was carried out. It has been established that the complex radiation and ultrasound diagnosis of hepatitis is carried out directly by the combined method. CT shows the condition of hollow organs better. Magnetic resonance imaging is usually the method of choice in the diagnosis of oncological and inflammatory liver diseases. Depending on the diagnostic goals set, the attending physician in each specific clinical case chooses the necessary research method or a combination of them.

Keywords: hepatitis, radiation examination, ultrasound examination, elastography, computed tomography, magnetic resonance imaging

Relevance. Hepatitis is an inflammatory liver disease of various, including viral etiology. Viral hepatitis is the most common liver disease [1, 2]. Every year in the world, 1-2 million people die from acute viral hepatitis alone. Chronic viral hepatitis is a group of infections caused by viruses that infect liver cells. The diagnosis of chronic hepatitis is made if the inflammatory process continues for more than six months [2]. Chronic hepatitis, especially of viral etiology, is considered by WHO as a serious public health problem, due to their global spread, long-term course, and adverse consequences.

The wide prevalence of this pathology and significant health disorders make it important and relevant to study and analyze the effectiveness of various methods of radiation diagnostics.

The purpose of the study. Analysis based on the data presented in the Internet sources of the effectiveness of the use of methods of radiation diagnosis of the liver in hepatitis.

The results of the study and their discussion. Ultrasound examination (ultrasound) is widely used in the diagnosis of liver diseases due to accessibility, noninvasiveness, absence of radiation loads [3]. However, the question of the diagnostic value of this method in chronic hepatitis remains open. The diagnostic value of ultrasound in hepatitis is limited – the sensitivity of the method is 58.4 %, the accuracy is 71.2 %. Ultrasound examination of the liver is not sufficient for the diagnosis of chronic hepatitis, assessment of its stage and activity, but due to its non-invasiveness, harmlessness and accessibility, it can be useful in establishing indications for further examination [3].

Liver elastometry is a modern diagnostic method that allows you to determine the degree of damage to liver tissue (fibrosis, cirrhosis) without surgery. If the purpose of ultrasound examination of the liver is to establish the presence of local (delimited) or diffuse (widespread) pathological changes in the structure of the organ, then the purpose of elastography is to determine the stage of fibrosis / cirrhosis of the liver.

Computed tomography (CT) of the liver is an informative and effective non-invasive study that is performed using X-rays [4].

Examination of the liver using computed tomography (CT) allows you to visualize the organ in layers, the cut-off step is millimeters, in some cases – tenths of millimeters [4]. CT of the liver is prescribed for the diagnosis of diseases, dynamic monitoring of the condition of the organ in chronic pathology, before planned surgical intervention in the hepatobiliary system, to monitor the condition after the operation. Computed tomography is an accurate method, but not safe due to the high radiation dose [4].

Computed tomography with contrast enhancement. CT with contrast is very accurate, allowing you to examine even the smallest tumors, blood clots and hematomas and is used when it is necessary to detail the picture of the disease [4]. CT with contrast is performed in cases where it is necessary to very clearly distinguish between normal and

abnormal structures in the human body. In addition, contrast is necessary to study the condition of blood vessels – veins, arteries [4].

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). Magnetic resonance imaging is the most effective method for liver examination. The study is most informative for the examination of parenchymal organs. The liver belongs to such organs, so MRI is widely used as a clarifying and complementary method in the complex diagnosis of complex diseases. Examination of the liver using MRI with contrast is performed after a little preparation, and shows high informativeness [5].

Magnetic resonance imaging is a complex and highly sensitive technique, so it is not prescribed in routine practice. Before doing an MRI of the liver with contrast, the patient is given other types of diagnostics (ultrasound, elastography, radiography). MR tomography is used for advanced diagnosis of diseases, if there are indications for this: the need for differential diagnosis between benign and malignant neoplasms; determination of the size and extent of spread of a malignant liver tumor; evaluation of the effectiveness of treatment; suspicion of a parasitic cyst, hemangioma or abscess that are poorly visualized on X-rays; suspicion of initial cirrhotic changes in liver tissue, deposition of pigments or other metabolic products.

Conclusions. Complex radiation and ultrasound diagnostics of hepatitis is carried out directly by a combined method, however, the diagnostic value of ultrasound is to some extent inferior to radiation diagnostic methods. CT shows the condition of hollow organs better. Magnetic resonance imaging is usually the method of choice in the diagnosis of oncological and inflammatory liver diseases. Depending on the diagnostic goals set, the attending physician in each specific clinical case chooses the necessary research method or a combination of them for the correct diagnosis and subsequent treatment of the patient.

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